

Learning Techniques for Acquiring Grain Farming Competencies: A Classic Grounded Theory

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South Africa's National Development Plan (NDP 2030) envisages to upskill many emerging farmers and upgrade them to commercial farming. The previously disadvantaged farmers comprise of this emerging category and above all, prospective farmers are also accommodated in the same category. This calls for learning to be transferred through any available means, for knowledge and skill seekers to benefit. This paper seeks to present findings on the learning techniques used to acquire grain farming competencies through employing classic grounded theory. Fifteen semi-structured interviews with participants comprising of farmers and farm workers were held in the study. Additionally, triangulation with three experts validated the learning techniques raised by the participants. Findings showed that early child exposure to farming, learning at educational institutions, openness to mentoring, on-the-job training and participating in refresher training programmes serve as important learning techniques. Theoretical and practical implications of the study are also discussed.

Keywords: Learning technique, grain farming, commercial farming, competency

Skill acquisition plays a vital role in every business. Subsistence farmers and emerging farmers need to acquire skills that will enable them to graduate to commercial farming. This calls for identifying the means through which these skills and knowledge should be used to transfer this learning process.

According to McElwee and Robson (2005), the nature of skills identifiable from farmers who present entrepreneurial orientation include (1) business and management skills such as accountancy, financial capability, strategic planning and people management, (2) co-operation and networking skills, (3) information technology skills, (4) marketing and selling skills, (5) entrepreneurial quality and values and (6) technical and professional skill such as exact farming skills. Another study conducted by Hill (2007) in Phelan (2014) generated set of skills ranging from business planning, financial management, people management, sales and marketing, collaboration, to leadership and risk management. Though the list outlines skills that are generally entrepreneurial in nature, they may also be described as business and management skills and competencies.

Hanna et al. (2012) suggest learning by noticing as a strategy farmers can adopt in acquiring skills. Seeing that the debate on farm entrepreneurial competency is still at an infancy stage, this paper is in a better position to positively contribute to this discussion particularly from an African point of view. Regarding the methodologies adopted in the previous studies, the classic grounded theory adopted in this paper brings a totally different perspective in the farm entrepreneurial competency discussion. Therefore, the purpose of this paper was to explore the learning techniques for

acquiring grain farming competencies using a classic grounded theory method.

Method

Glaser's classic grounded theory method was used in this investigation. Holton and Walsh (2017) offer three foundational pillars of classic grounded theory (GT) as emergence, constant comparative analysis and theoretical sampling. Emergence thus refers to the result of GT's open and exploratory stance in relation to the research field. Constant comparative analysis then refers to the process through which all data are analysed, as they are collected and together with all previously collected data. Theoretical sampling is the process through which empirical data are selected and collected as guided by the emerging theory.

A classic grounded theory uses two types of coding, i.e. substantive coding and theoretical coding, with the former preceding the latter. Hernandez and Andrews (2012) as well as Walker and Myrick (2006) refer to the substantive coding as having sub-phases of open and selective coding.

The constant comparative process involves three types of comparisons, namely: incident to incident for the emergence of concepts, concepts to more incidents for further theoretical elaboration, saturation and densification of concepts, and concepts to concepts for their emergent theoretical integration and through theoretical coding (Evans, 2013). According to Hernandez (2009), the memoing process helps the researcher to determine which of the theoretical codes provides the best relational model to integrate substantive codes to theoretical codes. Finally, Evans (2013) states that theoretical saturation is achieved by the constant comparison of incidents in the data to elicit the properties and dimensions of each category or code.

In the current study, a total of about fifteen interviews with farmers, former farmers and farm workers. Triangulation with three agriculture experts was conducted to confirm the findings. Jane McPherson (personal communication on 2014, October 06) suggested the following criteria for choosing eight commercial grain farmers as suitable participants for this study:

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- Had to be leasing or owning a farm.
- Farm location had access to travel and distribution infrastructure.
- Had developed the technical skills.
- Had ten or more permanent employees.

A further two participants who are farm managers were chosen based on the following criteria as suggested by McPherson:

- Had to be overseeing a leased or owned farm on behalf of the owner.
- Farm location had access to travel and distribution infrastructure.
- Had developed the technical skills.
- Had ten or more permanent employees.

According to Chaminuka et al. (2008, p. 368), "emerging farmers were defined as those previously disadvantaged farmers who are now participating in the market and are still facing some constraints to full participation." Ordinarily, these are the majority of Black African farmers falling in this category. So, for the purpose of this study, one participant who was classified as an emerging farmer (considered moderately successful) was chosen based on the following criteria, relying on the same sampling method as suggested by McPherson:

- Had to be leasing or owning a farm.
- Farm location had access to travel and distribution infrastructure.
- Had developed some technical skills.
- Had ten or fewer permanent employees.

An additional participant who was classified as a farmer who had a challenge that led the business stop operating (unsuccessful), was chosen based on the following criteria, relying on the same sampling method as suggested by McPherson:

- Had leased or owned a farm that is out of operation.
- Farm location had access to travel and distribution infrastructure.
- Had developed some technical skills.
- Had permanent employees in their payroll.

The participants' information was informed by reaching saturation, meaning that if gathered data repeats itself, further gathering of data would stop. As Bless et al. (2013) put it, using this method concentrates on getting information from the most extreme cases, highly unusual manifestations of the researched phenomenon, obviously not representative of the target population, may sometimes be the most revealing cases.

Purposive sampling of about three experts from main grain suppliers for the selected farmers were chosen based on the following criteria as suggested by McPherson:

- Had ten years or more in the field.
- Had advised a chosen farmer for five years or more.

Furthermore, about two farm workers were selected following the purposive sampling method based on meeting the following criteria as suggested by McPherson:

- Had been employed permanently.
- Had been employed by the current farmer for ten years or more.

The purposive sampling of experts and farm workers serves as a strategy to include units that are judged to be the most common in the population in this investigation.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical clearance to conduct this study was obtained from the University of the Free State in the Faculty of Economic and Management Sciences Ethics Committee on 01 September 2016.

The ethics number is UFS-HSD2016/0133.

Written informed consent was obtained from all individual participants involved in the study as the consent forms were signed. Confidentiality, privacy and anonymity were guaranteed to the participants.

Results and Discussion

This study took place in the province of the Free State, famously known in the farming sector as the breadbasket of the country. It is one of the nine provinces constituted in the Republic of South Africa. This province is demarcated into five district municipalities, which are: Thabo Mofutsanyana, Fezile Dabi, Xhariep, Motheo, and Lejweleputsa. The study was conducted in the district municipality of Thabo Mofutsanyana, which covers local municipalities such as Setsoto, Nketoana, Dihlabeng, Phumelela, and Maluti-a-Phofung. The focus was on Maluti-a-Phofung resulting from the fact that it was considered a poverty-stricken area by Statistics SA as it only had about 26% of employment with government being the major employer (Statistics SA, 2011) while the recent statistics showed that the provinces of Free State and North West experienced an increase in unemployment between quarter 2 and quarter 3 of 2023 to the level that is above the national rate (Statistics SA, 2023). This municipality is in the eastern part of the province and borders both the province of Kwa-Zulu Natal and Lesotho. In this way, the weather patterns happening in both borders have a major impact in what happens in this area, such as the heavy winter snows in Lesotho and some big summer rainfalls in Kwa-Zulu Natal.

About fifteen farmers agreed to take part in the study, twelve of whom were male black and only three were male white South Africans whose ages ranged from 30 years to 74 years old. All the farmers were involved in mixed type of farming, which means that they plant crops and breed the livestock, especially cattle and sheep, except only one who was strictly in livestock. The major grains planted in this district municipality are maize, dry-beans, sunflower, wheat and soya beans. Two participants do not own a farm but work on leased farms. Farm sizes for those who own them range from about 250 hectares to about just above 500 hectares. The positions of the participants on farms ranged from farmers themselves (farm owners) to farm managers (sons of farmers whose fathers were still very active on farm activities & decision making). Education levels of the participants ranged from no formal education to pursuing a master's degree in agriculture. About ten interviews were conducted in Sesotho except for two, where there was a mix of both Sesotho and English languages. Therefore, the tapes are recorded in original language and only the transcripts contain translated texts. The remaining three were done in English. All the transcripts amounted to about 98 typed pages of text that emerged from the interviews. Every effort has been made to keep the richness of the information shared in the interviews, while for the interviews conducted in both languages, efforts of translation were only done on the Sesotho part, leaving the English one verbatim. The length of the interviews lasted from about 24 minutes to about 96 minutes. All the participants in this investigation are considered successful grain farmers. I categorise them as such because of the recognition they received from GrainSA for producing high yields in certain crops such as maize.

Table 1 below summarises the demographic information of all research participants who voluntarily agreed to take part in this investigation. It displays their demographic information in the current study as told by themselves during the interview process that took place between the years 2017 and 2020.

Table 1
Summarised Demographic Information of the Research Participants

Interview date	Participant Identity	Participant status	Age	Race & Gender	Educational qualification	Are you a full-time bona fide farmer?	Number of years involved in farming	Do you own a farm or is it leased?	Farm size	Arable and grazing land	Live on farm or distance from home	Any livestock component on the farm?	Type of farming	Main crops planted	Do you have own farm implements?	How do you manage your farm implements?	Do you keep farming expenses records?	Are you a member of a farmer's organisation?	Are you part of any training and development programme?	What there a decline or increase in yield over the past three years?
2017-06-29	P1 Farm manager	35	Black Male	After grade 12, did LADP Courses at a University	Real farmer	15 years	Family- owned farm	407 ha	125 arable and 282 for grazing	Home and farm, home is 30 km away	There is livestock	Mixed farming but mainly producing crops	maize, soya, wheat dry beans & sunflower	There are implements	Self-managed, everything still needs to be Properly Inspected because many a times these Implements wear out	Yes	Do you keep farming expenses records?	Yes, I am a member of AFAASA	Do attend short courses offered by GrainSA	A decline by 40% resulting from drought no yield at all
2017-08-18	P2 Farmer	62	Black Male	Standard 8	Yes	Since 1988	Own ha	250 ha	160 ha arable and the rest is grazing	No but much of the time on farm, home is 20 km away & travel daily	60 heads of cattle	Mixed farming but mainly crop farming	Maize, dry-beans, wheat & soya beans	Yes, sorted in that angle	Self-managed, everything still needs to be Properly Inspected because many a times these Implements wear out	Yes	Do you keep farming expenses records?	Yes, I am a member of AFAASA	Do attend short courses offered by GrainSA	A decline by 40% resulting from drought no yield at all
2018-07-07	P3 Farmer	69	Black Male	No formal schooling	Yes	Since 1990	Own ha	360 ha	250 ha arable land and the rest is for Grazing	Sometimes but home is in Qwaqwa, distance is 15 km & travel daily	Yes, especially dairy cattle	Mixed farming, dairy and crop farming	Maize, beans and wheat and even soya	Yes, they have to be there	Around this time when we are done with the whole work, we look after them, fix everything, when rain comes you are not delayed by fixing them	Yes we keep them for tax purposes, and give them to book keepers	No these unions just take our money, we do not see what they do	There are GrainSA and Nestle for dairy	We did plant but drought hit us severely	
2019-02-16	P4 Farm manager	30	Black Male	Grade 11	Yes, it is in my blood	I did this since I was	Family- owned farm	408 ha	We live here on the farm	Yes, it is even dairy over	Mixed farming, dairy and crop	We plant mainly beans, maize,	Yes	Like that one we use to harvest beans, after	Yes, old man takes them to	I think is NAFU	I have been attending these	The past three years yields		

2020-02-27	P13 Farmer whose business went under	64	Black Male	Former professional nurse	Yes	up on a farm 25 years	Was own farm	356 ha	Home and on farm	There is livestock	Mixed farming crops and dairy	beans maize, soya, wheat dry beans & sunflower	There were implements	Did repairs	AFASA	Used to attend courses offered by GrainSA
2020-02-27	P14 Farmer	46	Black Male		Yes		Family-owned farm		Farm	No livestock	Crop farming only	Maize, wheat, dry-beans, soya	There are implements	We manage them ourselves	AFASA, VKB	Attend courses at GrainSA
2020-02-27	P15 Farmer	44	Black Male	Standard 9 now grade 11	Yes	Since 2002 after my father passed on	Family-owned farm	566 ha	Home and on farm	There is livestock mainly Bonsmara	Mixed farming	Maize, soya, beans	Have implements	Repair them myself	Netpu member, VKB, AFASA and Makholokoe Organisation and rural VKB, AFASA development and Makholokoe Organisation	GrainSA as well as some training by the department of agriculture

As can be seen from the sub-themes generated in the table above using a selective coding process, five methods emerged from the data. These methods as discussed below are early child exposure to farming, educational institutions, openness to mentoring, on-the-job training and refresher training.

Early Child Exposure to Farming

Study suggests that once children are exposed to the farming environment from an early age, chances of loving it will be high. Thus, one research participant (P15) made this remark

If you have a child and leave him or her at home he or she knows nothing. I say a child or children, let me put it this way I actually had been coming here on the farm as a child I had been rejoicing at driving tractors not knowing that one day I would be responsible.

Another participant (P1) took this further by including the fact that

as parents we should start our children from elementary level, if we want these children to be the best commercial farmers in twenty years' time we should ensure their foundation is right; by a right foundation I am referring to a situation where maybe as a father to a three-year-old son. I should be going out with him so that he could have passion for agriculture, I think that is what caused the white people to attain the stage they are as commercial farmers.

Albert Bandura in his self-efficacy theory asserted that vicarious learning or modelling is one of the determinants of self-efficacy. Vicarious experience or modelling is based on observation of another person who may be regarded as a role model, which includes the consequences of that role model's behaviour (Krekar & Coric, 2013). Although it was used in a different context, Taylor and Bhasme (2018, p. 1) argue that "Model farmers therein serve as a community repository of knowledge while also helping to translate and embed an agricultural innovation into local contexts." This finding proposes that if farmers expose their children to farming operations in their early years, such children stand a chance of developing love for the grain farming occupation.

On-the-job Training

On-the-job training is commonly known as learnership, internship or practical work where the learner acquires knowledge by doing it and learning from veterans in a practical setting. One research participant (P8) remarked

There are many people who went to agriculture schools. But they don't have the skill to practise it. That is where I said to you farming to me is a lifestyle, if you don't practise it you lose it.

Another participant (P7) confirmed the previous statement by adding that

They need to go to school but school alone is not enough, there is this thing I do not know what you call it after attending school? You call it practical in your language. What you were reading in books should now be done practically because this book cannot get in the field.

The other participant (P6) went further indicating that

I would suggest to get a solid young man, competent to start, he needs a lot of practical experience in this course that he is doing and physically see the things because it's all about seeing things. You come and you have to work your fields every day because you need to see the insects in there, and the plants that are taking strain, or there's a lot of grass, if I never came here the grass would be tall. It's very hands-on.

Table 2*Selective Coding Theme- Methods of Acquiring Grain Farming Competencies*

 Sub-theme: Early child exposure to farming environment

P1

- start our children from elementary level, if we want these children to be the best commercial farmers in twenty years' time we should ensure their foundation is right; by a right foundation I am referring to a situation where maybe as a father to a three-year-old son
- I should be going out with him so that he could have passion for agriculture, I think that is what caused the white people to attain the stage they are as commercial farmers

P15

- If you have a child and leave him or her at home he or she knows nothing
- I say a child or children, let me put it this way I actually had been coming here on the farm as a child I had been rejoicing at driving tractors not knowing that one day I would be responsible
- And I saw this as something so simple that even planting is not a problem but unaware of the costs involved, unaware of how long you wait

Sub-theme: Person's own preferred method

P2

- no best method because you need to know that these things change year in year out
- The best method is the one suitable to you

Sub-theme: Openness to mentorship

P2

- be in a position to know that you can be guided and you also be able to guide others

P4

- I think if he may approach them because asking is another form of acquiring skill

P6

- I won't say that, but you're gonna battle. Look, there's lots of help, but you can't... you must try and identify something and know why it does that.
- But you get a lot of help from your neighbours and you ask as well, but you first have to have that understanding to understand it.

Sub-theme: Practical training

P3

- If you read from books you will forget it, he has to be in a job and be determined

P6

- So to answer that question: do a course that can give you practical help as well because I feel your universities (I'm not mocking universities, my kids all went to university), but I saw it afterwards, when they are going into the working environment, they haven't seen the thing they learned about, especially farming because it's so hands-on.
- I would suggest to get a solid young man, competent to start, he needs a lot of practical experience in this course that he is doing and physically see the things because it's all about seeing things.
- You come and you have to work your fields every day because you need to see the insects in there, and the plants that are taking strain, or there's a lot of grass, if I never came here the grass would be tall.
- It's very hands-on.
- The course should be structured to be very hands-on and practical because it's a practical thing.
- You have to be hands-on, you have to be here, and you have to ensure that your stuff is proper then you'll get rewarded for that.
- It's like selling chappies: You sell one chappies you're not gonna get anything... so that's the same concept.
- So, you need to do it in volume. And the bigger you are, the more expensive it is, the more tools you need,

P7

- They need to go to school but school alone is not enough, there is this thing I do not know what you call it after attending school?
- You call it practical in your language
- What you were reading in books should now be done practically because this book cannot get in the field
- You need to practise what is said, yes, that is right, yes, it now comes to being

P8

- There are many people who went to agriculture schools
- But they don't have the skill to practise it
- That is where I said to you farming to me is a lifestyle, if you don't practise it you lose it
- So it doesn't help to have gone to school but not practise what you learned at school
- You will see once you start practising everything falls into place and your understanding becomes even much better when you practise than reading
- I don't know if I would saying they are the best but what I can say this is the best teacher, you said you look for method, didn't you?
- The first one is practice
- Practice makes perfect
- Mind we look for the best method if you want to be the best farmer
- You must practise to be a farmer as far as I am concerned
- What does practice mean? If you want to farm with cattle do cattle farming

- There is no other way do cattle farming
- And then training can better advance a person's understanding
- In order to be one of the best producers
- Training, I want to be honest to achieve the level you asked me when starting this interview as how can we encourage or motivate young people to be farmers?
- The time I have worked here in government I learned only those two things that nothing will liberate our people in agriculture without education
- And training followed by practice I advocate only three things, train, practice and then get someone you can call a coach or a role model
- That we will need if we want to build a developed society because in my Sesotho we say if you are riding a horse alone you could say it runs fast as it goes past the grass
- So you need to get a role model in order for us to make a continuous development of our practices, we need to get a person whom you look up to
- And say you want to be like him so you can advance, as far as I am concerned the best way of making farmers is practice
- And then training will increase understanding, training will not make people farmers but it will expand their understanding of some of the things they see or do
- So that when they perform they do so with a better understanding

P12

- You know to persevere farming a person must walk with someone who farms
- You see when you walk next to him
- You will learn many things and you will develop love for this
- But learning only what you do not love, aikhona, wait a bit
- Aikhona! I used to see young people walking about here on farms wanting to work here
- That was a good thing coming like this
- No, no, you waste your time.
- We milked, we did so many things about farming and we were doing them practically unaware that we do them so
- After school you would find us on tractors
- We knew all those things, digging up potatoes and all these things, you cannot cheat me, no I refuse
- You cannot because you know our children
- To show him how a farm operates you need to encourage and show him the importance of a thing
- That the importance is to do this and that, it because I see white people's children are so determined
- They take farming seriously
- Really we black people, when you check that now that these children are not going to school
- Do you know if you take them and go and work with them there?
- They will love it, I am telling you they will love it, they will love it really
- Yes, it because as we were growing up the farmer whom we were staying with
- When we are back from school he would put us at the back of his van
- And would just leave there in the fields and by then tractors are ploughing going up and down
- And we are so eager to jump on top of them
- You would find this wheat combine here, it would make you mad
- I would test any of them be it of wheat, maize, beans, sunflower, soya, no man, no
- That is what I loved about farming, that way we would spend much of our time in the fields
- All these chaps would now bother you by asking, when are we going there?
- Exactly, they even enjoy milking cows and they kick them there
- You put in love like that, that how we loved farming
- You see these people of GrainSA?
- Those are good people, they show their stuff on a television
- Those guys are good, they show you that this thing is done this way and that other one that way, never take that it is your own garden and you want to plant cabbage, no wait
- They will empower you, they will say man we are paying you a visit
- They will help you those guys and you will succeed
- You will succeed, their training is free of charge
- They show you that man do this, everything because there are many mixtures
- In so many things they will help you that man do this, do that

P14

- Learning through practice
- make time for refresher courses as technology changes swiftly

P15

- It is practical
- Yes practical, there are those who come here from schools
- Yes practical, it is the first one
- If you have a child and leave him or her at home he or she knows nothing

- I say a child or children, let me put it this way I actually had been coming here on the farm as a child I had been rejoicing at driving tractors not knowing that one day I would be responsible

Sub-theme: Educational institutions

P5

- Agricultural academies, universities, all institutions that are prepared to train you, you must go there
- Institutions, training, training, training, the best thing. Why training, good methods of planting give you high yields on a small scale
- If you don't train people, they think that in order to yield more, you must have a larger space, no, no, no; Profitability starts with a smaller scale. If your hectare is giving you 5 ton
- Then that is good for you, but if a hectare gives you zero comma one or comma five, then you are wasting land

P6

- Yeah you're gonna need a little bit of high-skill level as well because the terminologies that they use for plants is microbiology and things like that so you understand that you're gonna need a higher skill level
- You have to have a matric and at least go to a college.
- To understand because there's chemicals involved in this as well which you're going to have to understand (what's nitrogen? what does it do?) ... each and every one of them.
- So, like I said, to break it down, you're going to have the ability to understand it.
- So, you're have to have post-matric, at least.

P7

- You should know from here to the gate over there how many of the seed should be planted, so all those things require schooling
- Someone once made a fool of me where I even regretted not being educated, I knew that a bag of maize seed covers about 2 ha
- So this man asks me how many population am I going to plant, I then thought this now requires some school and he takes me for no know-how
- Now he takes me to the population
- I then said it needs education, today's farming needs education
- You need to know even the insecticides, truly whites did show us
- When should you spray using which insecticide, even when winter gets in you should know what changes to make, as all that is related to education,
- Mainly these chemicals to spray, especially beans you can be scared when these whites tell you about chemicals used, I wonder, let me show you some paper here
- I just want to show you that these things now need educated people, you see here they are even not enough
- You see all these are chemicals you are supposed to know how you should mix
- You see that thing, you must know how much should you pour in
- You see this two-time spray, all those things what I mean is that they must be known by someone who has been schooled, you see?
- All those insecticides you must know how to use them, there are so many of these things that exceed what you see here especially in beans
- Yes, these are things that you should know at least what you are going to do
- So when you check, it really needs one to go to school
- One really needs to go to school, and when he comes back to these dealing in chemicals, training there is necessary
- Where they would show you how a thing operates because if are not trained, chances are that you will burn maize or beans when spraying
- Right there is that easy way out from the one you buy chemicals to calculate for you that when your spray is like 800 litres you should pour in so much of this, all those things you should note down but know them so that when he is no longer there you are able to mix on your own
- Yes, but the truth is this thing needs education

Sub-theme: Refresher workshops

P2

- But what stands out is that they have their own unions where they receive training on the new methods of doing the thing I am used to, so you need to come closer and seek help and never work hard unnecessarily because sometimes what kills us is being used to working in a particular way, since old ways delay and have the understanding that having things like farmer's day
- Such things are sources of information
- As well as kinds of equipment where you see that this has improved the previous one and notice your environment needs such, so that is where you derive determination of improving your work

P5

- Another thing is farmer/s days. You call them boere dag
- That's where you get diamond.
- That's where you get diamond, it is not in the book

P14

- make time for refresher courses as technology changes swiftly

These sentiments were further confirmed by several other participants such as P3, P12, P14 and P15.

Especially for nascent entrepreneurs, in-service training which is an equivalent of on-the-job training, improves the performance of businesses. Suvedi et al. (2018) found this in-service training and other methods as appropriate for improving core competencies of agricultural extension workers but not farmers. So far I am not yet aware of the literature that supports how farmers manage on-the-job training as it happened in the current study.

Educational Institutions

Findings indicate that educational institutions are also available to impart knowledge to those willing to acquire grain farming competencies. These are agricultural schools, colleges and universities. Furthermore, these institutions need to incorporate a lot of practice in the theory taught. One research participant (P5) remarked that

Agricultural academies, universities, all institutions that are prepared to train you, you must go there. Institutions, training, training, training, the best thing. Why training, good methods of planting give you high yields on a small scale. If you don't train people, they think that in order to yield more, you must have a larger space, no, no, no; profitability starts with a smaller scale. If your hectare is giving you 5 ton, then that is good for you, but if a hectare gives you zero comma one or comma five, then you are wasting land.

Another participant (P6) confirmed this by remarking that

Yeah you're gonna need a little bit of high-skill level as well because the terminologies that they use for plants is microbiology and things like that so you understand that you're gonna need a higher skill level.

Research on human capital and rural entrepreneurship focusing on education, experience, knowledge and skill found a positive relationship between these human capital variables and success (Skuras et al., 2005). This finding is validated by the recommendations in a survey which investigated farmer knowledge and perception of production constraints in Cambodia which had included droughts and heavy rain, declining crop yields and cash flow shortages. Farmer education was recommended for them to learn more about the non-traditional methods of conservation agriculture (Montgomery et al., 2017). Khapayi and Celliers's (2016) support this finding by stating that low education levels among emerging farmers inhibits them from becoming commercial farmers which eventually results in an inability to interpret market information to be used in production planning and marketing. Terblanché (2006) recommended that *that in order to develop a new generation of farmers as well as agriculturists, not only should the Education Department carry the responsibility, but all role players should take charge in the formation of coordinating structures and linkages, participation in agricultural projects for learners, development of new programmes for learners in all schools and college level. The role of educational institutions in upskilling the society is paramount as it is shown in the current study as well as being validated by previous studies.*

Openness to Mentorship

This refers to willingness and openness to mentor others or willing to learn from those who made it in life. Willingness in this aspect would fulfil service to humanity, which similarly translates into social responsibility to lift those lower in the ranks in society. One research

participant (P6) made this comment

But you get a lot of help from your neighbours and you ask as well, but you first have to have that understanding to understand it.

Another participant (P2) went further indicating that a farmer should “be in a position to know that you can be guided and you also be able to guide others” while the other one (P4) emphasised the previous point by adding that

I think if he may approach them because asking is another form of acquiring skill.

Šūmane and colleagues (2018, p. 239) argue that “Personal curiosity and willingness to learn, together with social networking, farmers' organisations, and supportive formal knowledge and governance structures, are central elements for successful learning, integrating knowledge and innovating for sustainability.” As far as the finding on this aspect goes, not only does willingness fulfil self-actualising, it also serves as a farmer's social responsibility role from the business side. Mentorship is found to play a significant role in the transfer of knowledge and skill from the expert to the trainee (Terblanché, 2011).

Refresher Workshops

Attending refresher workshops was raised by several participants and among them P5 commented

Another thing is farmers' days. You call them 'boere dag'. That's where you get diamond. That's where you get diamond, it is not in the book.

The refresher workshop was also supported by P1, P2 and P14.

Learning in any occupation is a continuous process which is enhanced mainly by attending refresher workshops in order to be up to date with the current trends in one's trade. This finding is validated by the recommendations in a survey where Khapayi and Celliers (2016) investigated factors limiting and preventing emerging farmers to progress to commercial agricultural farming in the Eastern Cape in South Africa where they advise government to provide planned workshops to all farmers in order to equip them with marketing knowledge.

Conclusion

This paper found that the love for farming can develop once children are exposed to the farming environment at an early age. On-the-job training refers a situation where a trainee acquires knowledge and skill by doing and learning from veterans in a practical setting. Educational institutions such as agricultural schools, colleges and universities are places available to impart knowledge to those willing to acquire grain farming competencies. Openness to mentorship refers to willingness and openness to mentor others or willing to learn from those who made it in life or occupation. Attending refresher workshops shapes and sharpens the farmer's knowledge and skills regarding the current trends and developments in one's trade because learning in any occupation is a continuous process.

I further recommend the use of surveys with bigger samples in order to construct a standardised instrument that could measure each of the themes developed in this model and test its applicability on future prospective grain farmers. Moreover, I do recommend testing hypotheses raised in this study as to whether methods of acquiring grain competencies including the competencies themselves do lead to success indicated in the study.

It is noteworthy that the grounded theory route is less travelled. Therefore, I do recommend that researchers consider adopting any methods within the grounded theory approach where formulation of typologies or frameworks would be realised particularly in the management studies.

Many previous studies have developed exact competencies for different occupations or jobs including some in the agricultural sector. Therefore, unlike other studies that developed competencies for various occupations even for some in the agricultural sector, the current study came up with different skills, knowledge and personal attributes that broadly form general competencies for commercial grain farming.

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